

NFDI 4
BIODIVERSITY
BIODIVERSITY, ECOLOGY & ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

Report on available cross-cutting services with NFDI4Biodiversity involvement

Strategic Report for Milestone 2.1.4

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Executive Summary

Base services offer generic functionalities that many or even all NFDI consortia require as part of the operation regardless of their scientific domain. So far nine different base services have been funded and are at different stages of their maturity. Most of them have a moderate or high integration potential with NFDI4Biodiversity and in most of them partners of NFDI4Biodiversity are involved in various forms, in several cases even as co applicants.

The most important Basic Services from a NFDI4Biodiversity perspective are:

- **IAM4NFDI**: Basic Service for Identity and Access Management (*GWDG: co-applicant*)
- **TS4NFDI**: Basic Service for Harmonization and mapping of terminologies (*InfAI: co-applicant*)
- **DMP4NFDI**: NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans
- **Jupyter4NFDI**: A Central JupyterHub for the NFDI
- **PID4NFDI**: Basic Service for Persistent Identifier Services (*several partners involved*)
- **KGI4NFDI**: Basic Service for Knowledge Graph Infrastructures
- **nfdi.software**: NFDI Research Software Marketplace
- **RDMTraining4all**: Basic Service for Competence Training for Research Data Management

Introduction

NFDI4Biodiversity

NFDI4Biodiversity is a well-established consortium within NFDI. Thanks to the predecessor project GFBio, NFDI4Biodiversity could rely on a solid foundation of well-connected partners, tools, and procedures to ensure a smooth start in the NFDI landscape.

With its leading role, NFDI4Biodiversity and its partners are well-connected within the NFDI ecosystem. This shows in the Base4NFDI services, with most of the services having active involvement of one or more NFDI4Biodiversity partners.

Base4NFDI

Base services offer generic functionalities that many or sometimes even all NFDI consortia require as part of their operation regardless of their scientific domain. They are small projects that are proposed by the NFDI sections and receive funding for short periods.

Service maturity is reflected by the phase in which a basic service is. The three phases are: Initialization Phase (Phase 1), Integration Phase (Phase 2) and Ramp-Up Phase (Phase 3). Each phase requires a new proposal to be submitted during one of the regular funding rounds.

During the funding rounds, the NFDI consortia are invited to give feedback to the proposals, judging their usefulness, project structure, required resources, etc.

As of September 2025 there have been nine funding rounds with 15 basic services that applied for funding. Nine of these services have been funded so far, at different stages. A complete overview of all the projects, the funding rounds, and which proposals were approved can be found in Appendix A.

Methods

As part of the second phase proposal for NFDI4Biodiversity all of the approved Base4NFDI services were evaluated with regard to their potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity. Within the second funding phase in TA5M3, these assessments will be regularly reevaluated and updated to accommodate new developments and needs.

In the following chapter the eight basic services that received a moderate or high rating for their potential for integration are listed with a short profile listing:

- a **short description** of the service,
- a **URL for further** information,
- which **phase** they are in and during which round they were **funded**
- the **potential for integration** based on the evaluation done for the second phase proposal. In some cases these evaluations have been extended or updated for this document. Task Areas (TA) and Measures (M) refer to those from the second phase proposal.
- the **partners of NFDI4Biodiversity** that actively contribute to the basic service, sometimes mentioning the specific persons involved.

The services are ordered according to their potential for integration. Services that received the same integration potential rating are ordered by the round of their first successful proposal.

Base4NFDI Services

IAM4NFDI

Short description	Basic Service for Identity and Access Management
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/iam4nfdi

Funded since	R1: Initialization, R3: Integration, R9: Ramp-Up
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	<p>high</p> <p>In the Integration Phase of IAM4NFDI, we checked how the common Life Science Login, which is used by our service providers, ELIXIR, and other international initiatives, can be integrated into the IAM Services. Our partner GWDG (co-applicant of IAM4NFDI) and BIBI (part of the German Bioinformatics Network de.NBI, the German ELIXIR Node) play an important role in these efforts. In the second funding phase of NFDI4Biodiversity, we want to introduce a community AAI (Access and Authentication Infrastructure) as part of the Research Data Commons platform, in which an AAI Service Steward will administer the virtual organisations and user groups (TA3M4). A close synchronisation and integration with IAM4NFDI are considered strategically relevant for this endeavor.</p>
Involved NFDI4Biodiversity Partners	GWDG - Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliches Datenverarbeitung (GFBio Identity Provider), as co-applicant (through their partnership in NFDI4Ing)

TS4NFDI

Short description	Basic Service for Harmonization and mapping of terminologies
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/ts4nfdi
Funded since	R2: Initialization, R6: Integration
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	<p>high</p> <p>Our consortium partner InfAI is a co-applicant of this basic service and provides a solution for community created terminologies in the form of the BiodivPortal (https://biodivportal.gfbio.org/). The integration in TS4NFDI is planned as part of TA2M1.</p>
Involved Partners	Adrian Paschke, Naouel Karam, InfAI - Institut für Angewandte Informatik e.V. as co-applicant.

DMP4NFDI

Short description	NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/dmp4nfdi
Funded since	R4: Initialization, R7: Integration
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	<p>high</p> <p>GFBio contributes biodiversity aspects of DMPs to the efforts of DMP4NFDI, to harmonise DMP content across disciplines and to build a central service for hosting DMP tools as well as a central DMP help desk for NFDI. We imagine a redirect for institutions, who are interested in a Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) instance in Base4NFDI. GFBio, IPK and other NFDI4Biodiversity partners have running RDMO instances at their disposal and could offer community specific support for the development of workflows and content. GFBio is also going to contribute by providing training and the development of RDMO functionalities.</p>
Involved Partners	Jimena Linares & Ivaylo Kostadinov, GFBio e.V

Jupyter4NFDI

Short description	A Central JupyterHub for the NFDI
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/jupyter4nfdi
Funded since	R4: Initialization, R8: Integration
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	<p>high</p> <p>There are several established decentralised JupyterHub instances, which are run by consortium partners, some of which are involved in Jupyter4NFDI through other consortia (e.g. GWDG, UFZ, JLU and other universities). Access to those instances is usually restricted to a subgroup of users within NFDI4Biodiversity. We plan to use custom tailored notebooks (including data and preconfigured libraries) in the Research Data Commons (TA4). Smaller notebooks will also be used for training events in TA1M4.</p>
Involved Partners	GWDG - Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliches Datenverarbeitung, as institution, though not from an

	NFDI4Biodiversity angle
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PID4NFDI

Short description	Basic Service for Persistent Identifier Services
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi
Funded since	R2: Initialization, R6: Integration
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	<p>moderate-high</p> <p>The partner of NFDI4Biodiversity use underlying services and technologies that are central to PID4NFDI (such as DOI or IGSN). In addition, there is a highly domain-specific object identification system from the taxonomic community. The integration of the results into the work programme will be discussed and will be communicated through the PID4NFDI co-applicant GWDG.</p>
Involved Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GWDG - Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliches Datenverarbeitung, as one of two lead institutions (through their partnership with Text+) • IPK - Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research, as use case partner • DSMZ - Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen, as use case partner • SUB - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen, as use case partner

KGI4NFDI

Short description	Basic Service for Knowledge Graph Infrastructures
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/kgi4nfdi
Funded since	R4: Initialization
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	moderate

	While none of the NFDI4Biodiversity partners are involved in this basic service, there is a thematic overlap with the work on the knowledge graphs done in TA4M2 in the second funding phase. We will closely follow the activities of this basic service, and might adjust the work of our measure depending on its outcome.
Involved Partners	none

nfdi.software

Short description	NFDI Research Software Marketplace
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/nfdi-software
Funded since	R5: Initialization
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	moderate We generally recommend to our community the ELIXIR registry https://biotools.org , however we also need a community specific tool to promote our service catalogue (TA3). nfdi.software is planning the development of a tool, which can be used by consortia to create such community specific instances. The tool is expected to be available in 2027. We will consider this time frame and align all of the solutions developed within TA3M4 accordingly, so that they will be compatible with the solution of the basic service project.
Involved Partners	Maria Meister, GFBio e.V.

RDMTraining4NFDI

Short description	Competence Training for Research Data Management
URL	https://base4nfdi.de/projects/rdmtraining4nfdi
Funded since	R6: Initialization
Potential for integration with NFDI4Biodiversity	moderate RDMTraining4NFDI aligns with our goals by offering tailored research data management training,

	consultancy on didactic approaches, FAIR-compliant templates, and a trainer exchange network. Integration will strengthen our capacity-building efforts, foster cross-consortia collaboration, and avoid duplication of work, ultimately supporting a sustainable, community-driven RDM training infrastructure across the NFDI
Involved Partners	Frank Oliver Glöckner, AWI

Further resources

- Base4NFDI Website: <https://base4nfdi.de/>
- NFDI4Biodiversity internal list of basic services and the partners that are actively involved in them:
<https://kb.gfbio.org/display/NFDI/NFDI-weite+Basisdienste> (in German)
- D. Obeth, J. Biela, P. Scheiber, L. Stoy & N. Wilke (2025). Evaluation of Base4NFDI: Final Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16893487>
- Konsortialversammlung des Vereins Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V. (2022). Stellungnahme der NFDI-Konsortien zu Basisdiensten. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6091657> (in German)

Appendix A - Base Service Proposal Timeline

Name	Description	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9
		2023-02	2023-05	2023-08	2024-02	2024-05	2024-08	2025-01	2025-04	2025-07
IAM4NFDI	Basic Service for Identity and Access Management	Init (A)		Integ (A)						Ramp (A)
TS4NFDI	Basic Service for Harmonization and mapping of terminologies	Init (R)	Init (A)				Integ (A)			
PID4NFDI	Basic Service for Identity and Access Management	Init (R)	Init (A)				Integ (A)			
KGI4NFDI	Basic Service for Knowledge Graph Infrastructures	Init (R)			Init (A)			Integ (D)		
DMP4NFDI	NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans	Init (R)			Init (A)			Integ (A)		
HaDES	Harvesting and Findability Enhancing Services	Init (R)								
RDMTraining 4NFDI	Competence Training for Research Data Management			Init (R)			Init (A)			Integ (R)
Jupyter4NFDI	A Central JupyterHub for the NFDI			Init (R)	Init (A)					Integ (A)
nfdi.software	NFDI Research Software Marketplace			Init (R)		Init (A)				Integ (R)
MC4NFDI	A Multicloud Infrastructure for the NFDI						Init (R)	Init (R)		
DALIA4NFDI	Platform for Data Literacy Education and Training Resources							Init (R)	Init (R)	
nfdi.architecture	Requirements of NFDI consortia towards									Init (R)

	an Overall Architecture	
Support4RDM	A federated helpdesk network and RDM support infrastructure	Init (R)
ASSURED	Service for the safe and ethical use of sensitive data for the research community	Init (R)
Accounting 4NFDI	Accounting infrastructures for NFDI	Init (A)

Abbreviations

R1 .. R9	Funding Rounds
Init	Initialization Phase (Phase 1)
Integ	Integration Phase (Phase 2)
Ramp	Ramp-Up Phase (Phase 3)
A	Accepted
R	Rejected
D	Delayed